

DIPOLE MOMENTS FROM DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS OF LIQUIDS. PART II

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Dielectric constants, refractive indices and densities of a series of substances likely to contain a hydrogen bond have been measured at different temperatures and the moments calculated by using Onsager's equation. The values of dipole moments of substances forming intermolecular bonds show large deviations from values obtained by other methods. On the other hand the values of moments of substances forming an internal hydrogen bond agree with those obtained by other methods. Evidence of internal hydrogen bond has been supplied by determination of molecular weights cryoscopically.

In Part I the dipole moments of a number of non-associated compounds have been determined from their dielectric constants and the applicability of Onsager's equation to such a calculation has been proved. In this paper the dipole moments of a number of compounds likely to form a hydrogen bond have been calculated using the same method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—All the substances used were either purchased or prepared by standard methods and purified before use. The apparatus and the method of calculation have been described in Part I and the moments are expressed in Debye units.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three types of hydrogen bonding may be distinguished amongst organic compounds.

- (1) Intermolecular hydrogen bond resulting in 'unlimited association' and forming chain-like molecules as in alcohols, phenols, water, etc.
- (2) The inter-molecular hydrogen bonding leading to a definite dimer formation as in carboxylic acids.
- (3) Intramolecular hydrogen bonding formed by the presence of strong electro-negative substituents in close proximity to the hydrogen atoms. This type of compounds is also called chelated compounds. Salicylaldehyde, *o*-chlorophenol, *o*-nitrophenol etc. are examples of this type.

The following table records the results for compounds containing intermolecular hydrogen bond.

TABLE IA
Substances containing intermolecular hydrogen bond.

Substance.	Temp.	Dielectric constant.	Density.	Refractive index.	μ (Gas.)	μ (Sol.)	Diff.	Ref.
Water	25°	83.2	0.9995		3.11	1.84	1.84	1
<i>Primary alcohols</i>								
Methyl alcohol	20	34.0	0.792	1.324	3.01	1.60	1.32	3
Ethyl alcohol	20	23.8	0.789	1.361	2.92	1.67	1.25	3
	70	17.6	0.7456		2.84			1
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	20	22.2	0.804	1.386	3.09	1.58	1.51	3
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	20	17.4	0.8098	1.3992				3
	30	15.693	0.7943	1.3955	2.93	1.7	1.23	
<i>iso</i> Butyl alcohol	30	15.691	0.8083	1.3869	2.93	1.7	1.23	
<i>n</i> -Octyl alcohol	20	10.34	0.8253	1.420	3.02	1.7	1.32	3
Ethylene glycol	20	39.8	1.115	1.4318	3.49	2.28	1.21	3
Propylene glycol	20	32.0	1.038	1.4323	3.63	2.25	1.38	3
Trimethylene glycol	20	35.0	1.053	1.4396	4.21	2.5	1.71	3
Ethylene glycol monomethyl ether	30	15.95	0.9532	1.3977	2.74	2.2**	0.54	
Ethylene glycol mono-acetate	30	12.95	1.0665	1.4150	2.63	2.34**	0.29	

**These values have been taken from Gokhale, Phalnikar and Bhawe (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1943, 11, p. 56).

TABLE IB

Secondary alcohols

Substance.	Temp.	Dielectric constant.	Density.	Refractive index.	μ (Ons.)	μ (Sol.)	Diff.	Ref.
cycloHexanol	30°	14.737	0.9554	1.4579	2.83	1.9	0.93	3
	35	14.147	0.9507	1.4565	2.83			
	45	12.531	0.9411	1.4532	2.83			
o-Methylcyclohexanol	30	11.040	0.9260	1.4583	2.56	1.95	0.61	
	35	10.040	0.9247	1.4550	2.49			
	40	9.239	0.9222	1.4539	2.37			
m-Methylcyclohexanol	30	11.633	0.9131	1.4538	2.5	1.89	0.61	
	35	11.032	0.9113	1.4524	2.48			
p-Methylcyclohexanol	30	11.992	0.9111	1.4532	2.7	1.87	0.83	
	35	11.481	0.9088	1.4524	2.66			
o-Cresol	25	11.479	1.0315	1.5353	2.32	1.46	0.84	
	30	10.937	1.0281	1.5334	2.28			
m-Cresol	25	11.749	1.0175	1.5294	2.36	1.6	0.78	
	30	11.237	1.0145	1.5273	2.35			
Methyl heptanol	20	3.37	0.8348			1.62	1.36	2

TABLE IC

Tertiary alcohols

Substance.	Temp.	Dielectric constant.	Density.	Refractive index.	μ (Ons.)	μ^* (Sol.)	Diff.	Ref.
Tertiary butyl alcohol	20°	10.9	0.777	1.3878	1.74	1.65	0.09	3
Tertiary amyl alcohol	30	6.695	0.8061	1.3932	1.94	1.83	0.11	
	40	6.443	0.8084	1.3906	1.93			

Some of the above results have been collected from literature for the purposes of calculation. The number in the last column refers to the following references:—

1. Böttcher, *Physica*, 1938, 6, 635.
2. Smyth and Stoops, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 3310.
3. Morgan and Yager, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1940, 32, 1519.

*Values of the moments by the solution method have been taken from the table of Dipole moments, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934.

It will be seen from the table given above that in the case of water and other primary alcohols the moments obtained by the Onsager equation are approximately 3, while those obtained by the solution method are about 1.6 to 1.9. The difference in the values of the moments obtained by the two methods is 1.2 to 1.5.

The cyclohexanols and cresols are included as secondary alcohols. The cresols will behave as secondary alcohols because of resonance. In the case of these secondary alcohols the difference in the values of moments obtained by the solution method and the Onsager equation are 0.7 to 0.9 units higher as contrasted with 1.2 in the case of primary alcohols.

The case of tertiary alcohols is very interesting. Here the moments obtained by both the methods agree very well.

These differences can be very well accounted for if the nature of association is taken into account. In the primary alcohols the intermolecular hydrogen bond leads to unlimited association and formation of chain-like molecules. The resultant dipole moment of such chain-like molecules will depend upon the extent of association and the valency angles. Generally in the liquid condition the moments of such chain-like molecules will be higher than those for the simple molecules.

In a solution of these compounds in a non-polar solvent the hydrogen bond will be broken and hence the compound will be split up into normal molecules. The moment determined by the solution method will therefore be generally lower than that determined by the Onsager method as has been observed.

In the secondary alcohols the intermolecular hydrogen bond will be present but the extent of association here will be less than that in primary alcohols. The moments obtained by the two methods will not be the same, but the difference will be less than that in the case of primary alcohols as the extent of association is less.

The moments obtained by the two methods in the case of tertiary alcohols agree and are not vitiated by the presence of hydroxylic group. This is due to the fact that intermolecular hydrogen bond formation is prevented in tertiary alcohols due to steric hindrance. In tertiary amyl and butyl alcohols for example, the hydroxylic group being surrounded by three alkyl groups the chain forming tendency is hindered.

The spectroscopic examination of tertiary compounds supports this view. The spectroscopic examination of amyl alcohols (Badger and Bauer, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 843, 852) shows appreciable absorption characteristic of monomer in addition to broad polymer bands in the liquid condition. This monomer absorption is greatest in tertiary alcohols, decreases with a secondary one and is the least with the primary alcohols. The formation of chain-like associated molecules, a characteristic of primary alcohols and to a lesser extent in secondary alcohols, is not possible in the case of tertiary alcohols due to steric hindrance.

It may be noted that the greatest association in primary and secondary alcohols results in abnormal properties such as abnormal molecular weights, parachor, boiling points etc.

The following table gives the molecular weights of some of these compounds determined cryoscopically in benzene. Column two of the table gives the molecular weights actually obtained and column three, the formula weights.

TABLE II

Compound.	Molecular weight	
	obs.	calc.
<i>m</i> -Cresol	124	108
<i>cyclo</i> Hexanol	119	100
<i>o</i> -Methyl <i>cyclo</i> hexanol	137	114
<i>m</i> -Methyl <i>cyclo</i> hexanol	139	114
<i>p</i> -Methyl <i>cyclo</i> hexanol	140	114
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	128	128.5
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	134	128.5
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	138	139.0

It will be seen that the first five compounds (belonging to the secondary alcohol type) show abnormal molecular weights even in dilute benzene solutions, a characteristic of intermolecular hydrogen bonding liquids. *o*-Chlorophenol and *o*-nitrophenol show normal molecular weights in benzene solutions as these substances form intra-molecular hydrogen bonds, *p*-chlorophenol on the other hand shows a higher molecular weight as it can form a weak intermolecular hydrogen bond (*cf.* Pauling, *loc. cit.*).

The following table gives the results obtained in the case of a few *intra*-molecular hydrogen bonding liquids.

TABLE III

Substance.	Temp.	Dielectric constant.	Density.	Refractive index.	μ (Oms.)	μ (Sol.)	Diff.	Ref.
o-Chlorophenol	30°	6.163	1.2382	1.5475	1.56	1.43	0.11	(1)
	35	6.0628	1.2297	1.5446	1.53			
	40	5.914	1.2239	1.5429	1.55			
p-Chlorophenol	55	9.358	1.2663	1.5419	2.12	2.27	0.13	(1)
	60	9.185	1.2629	1.5388	2.10			
	65	8.983	1.2583	1.5361	2.08			
o-Nitrophenol	50	17.342	1.2823	1.5723	3.01	3.10	0.09	(1)
	55	17.025	1.2765	1.5708	3.01			
	60	16.703	1.2712	1.5690	3.01			
Salicylaldehyde	30	17.091	1.1654	1.4701	3.08	3.13	0.05	(2)
	35	16.658	1.1606	1.4680	3.07			
	40	16.374	1.1569	1.4661	3.05			
Methyl salicylate	30	8.443	1.1739	1.4299	2.33	2.41	0.08	(1)
	35	8.316	1.1684	1.5266	2.34			
	40	8.129	1.1635	1.5240	2.35			
Ethyl salicylate	30	7.99	1.1190	1.5070	2.80	2.88	0.08	(1)
	35	7.881	1.1145	1.5041	2.83			
	40	7.793	1.1107	1.5002	2.85			

The following is a list of references for dipole moments obtained by solution or gas method, taken from literature and referred to in the last column of the tables used in the above discussion.

(1) Table of dipole moments, *Trans. Faraday. Soc.*, 1934.

(2) Present work, Part I of this series.

From the table above it will be observed that the moments obtained by the Onsager equation and those obtained by the solution method do not differ much in the case of chelated compounds.

All these compounds, (excepting *p*-chlorophenol) have a tendency towards chelation. The presence of strong *intra*-molecular hydrogen bond in these liquids is indicated by their absorption spectra (Pauling, "Nature of the Chemical Bond," p. 323, Cornell University Press).

In the case of *o*-chlorophenol there is also a tendency to form dimers but this tendency will always be suppressed by the presence of the *cis*-form of *o*-chlorophenol constituting 90 per cent. of the substance (Pauling, *loc. cit.*). Spectroscopic examination of *o*-chlorophenol shows that this *cis*-form is present to the extent of 90% in the liquid.

In the chelated compounds there is no intermolecular bond both in the liquid condition or in solution in a non-polar solvent. Hence the moments obtained by the Onsager equation, *i.e.* in the liquid condition or by the solution method will not be different, a fact borne out by experiments.

In *p*-chlorophenol there will be a tendency to form dimers but the results as compared with other chelated compounds show that in *p*-chlorophenol the dimer formation is small.

CONCLUSION

The Onsager equation gives correct values for dipole moments of liquids which are not associated. Abnormally high values of dipole moments are obtained generally in the case of hydroxyl compounds which form indefinite chain polymers in the liquid condition due to the formation of hydrogen bonds. The equation, therefore, can be safely used to calculate the dipole moments from the dielectric constants of liquids excepting the associated liquids.